

SEAKNOT: LOOKING AHEAD OF SEVERE ACCIDENT RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

Severe Accidents (SAs) dominate the risk associated to the commercial production of nuclear energy. Despite the major achievements made in their research, still existing gaps, upcoming new technologies as Accident Tolerant Fuels (ATFs) and Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), more stringent safety requirements, optimization of SA management, and other factors, point the need for an efficient use of research resources in the years to come. Three major elements should integrate any SA roadmap to be proposed: preservation of knowledge and know-how; identification of key issues which research would result in the best accident management (AM) feasible; and, no less important, strengthening the workforce who will be responsible for such research. The SEAKNOT project (SEvere Accident research and KNOWledge managementT for LWRs) was born to address this need in all and every aspect. The present article outlines the major pillars of SEAKNOT and synthesizes the progress made since its onset at the end of 2022. The methodologies adopted to develop a SA PIRT (Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table) and to build a Validation Database Directory (VADD) are described along with the ongoing phenomena listing and ranking. Besides, the first steps towards an experimental infrastructure capable of dealing with present and future needs (SAINET) are included. No less relevant the actions already made and the novelties coming on the side of knowledge and know-how transfer are also discussed.

KEYWORDS

Severe Accident PIRT, knowledge and knowhow transfer, data and infrastructures

1. INTRODUCTION

Severe accidents are known to dominate the risk associated to the commercial production of nuclear power. A vast amount of research has been done in this field after the TMI2 accident in 1979. Preservation of knowledge and know-how gathered, though, might be at stake at present because of the retirement of senior scientists and engineers and the loss of access to old archives. At the same time, innovation in nuclear technologies (i.e., SMRs and ATFs) and in severe accident analysis, i.e., Uncertainty and Sensitivity Analysis (UaSA) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), might mean a change in the SA paradigm. These factors, along with the progressive reduction of resources in SA, stand out timeliness of critically review the

knowledge acquired to project a SA research roadmap that result in an efficient reduction and understanding of accident unfolding and, consequently, an optimization of AM. A key element to achieve the goal is to involve and enable young scientists and engineers by conducting a proper transfer of both knowledge and knowhow. These are the major drivers underneath the EURATOM SEAKNOT project (GA 101060327 [1]), which is coordinated by CIEMAT and participated by a total of 16 European organizations plus 1 associated partner (PSI) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. European countries and organizations participating in SEAKNOT

Accordingly, SEAKNOT pursues three major objectives: carrying out a sound and critical analysis of the current knowledge on SAs, including both existing (Gen II and Gen III) and forthcoming nuclear technologies (SM LWRs & ATFs); identifying experimental research needs required to support any further research resulting from the critical analysis; and strengthening the background and skills of young generations in the field.

The next sections describe SEAKNOT methodology, partnership and structure. Likewise, an overview of the current status of the project, one almost half-way to the end, will be given, including all what has been done and is planned concerning the K2T (Knowledge and Knowhow Transfer).

2. METHODOLOGY

The SEAKNOT methodology heavily relies on senior expertise. Bringing together senior experts with diverse perspectives (i.e., researchers, regulators, industry, academia ...) and mind-sets is an essential element to achieve a sound critical assessment that are not biased by the lack of sufficient background or the “research inertia” of keeping “business-as-usual”. This relevance is also fundamental when transferring the best knowledge and know-how to young researchers.

The backbone of SEAKNOT is the Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table (PIRT) that will be produced together with consolidated information on the experimental database and critical SA experimental infrastructure. It is worth highlighting that the PIRT will be grounded on State Of the Art (SOAR) reports recently issued, previous global and partial PIRT exercises, and the outcomes of open research projects since practically the beginning of this century. All sources of information will be considered, particularly those stemming from activities conducted in the frame of SNETP/NUGENIA Technical Area 2 [2-5].

Figure 2 shows the conceptual methodology of SEAKNOT. The PIRT development is the central activity. Once the fundamental SA library, which will consist of a list of the references used for the individual PIRT in each SA domain (i.e., in-vessel, ex-vessel, containment and source term) is gathered, the main sources of relevant data will be identified and employed to characterize the existing knowledge on the matter under

study. Through the expertise that will be available within the project, both the safety significance as well as the existing modelling capabilities of the phenomena under study will be assessed according to the PIRT methodology [6-8].

Figure 2. Sketch of SEAKNOT conceptual methodology

The SEAKNOT methodology results in a work-package (WP) structure (Figure 2), which is briefly described next. Four WPs were set plus the WP5 PROC on Project coordination. The PIRTSA WP (WP1) aims at developing the PIRT, with a specific sub-WP (WP1.1) devoted to set a methodology and the other sub-WPs (WP1.2-WP1.5) to its application in the in-vessel, ex-vessel, containment, and source term domains. The VADD WP (WP2) structure is practically identical to WP1 but its focus is the SA database (DB) to finally provide a sort of DB directory for SA codes validation. Note the strong interaction of VADD (Validation Database Directory) and PIRTSA, as input on available representative data is one of the pillars of the PIRT. WP3 SAINET (Severe Accident experimental Infrastructure NETWORK) plans to build a map of experimental infrastructures in Europe with potential to be used in the coming years, as well as to identify what sort of facility should be set up to address some of the primary PIRT issues, if none of the existing ones can do it. Finally, WP4 KNOS responds to the SEAKNOT need of a powerful WP for dissemination, communication, and exploitation of the project results, also in the view of an effective K2T to young generations of researchers and technicians.

Figure 3. SEAKNOT work-packages, work flow and major outcomes

This work structure in Fig. 3 gets embedded in the project governance, in which the project Executive Board (ExB), which is integrated by the project and WPs coordinators, interact with two project supporting bodies:

Advisory Body (AB), consisting mostly of regulators and TSO experts; and, End User Group (EUG), where external Agencies (NEA, IAEA, and ENEN) involved in SA research and education and training are involved. Both of them will follow closely the project. The former will specifically bring in substantiated assessment on phenomena safety relevance. The latter might be instrumental in two major aspects: orchestrating ongoing activities and projects under their frames with SEAKNOT activities, and helping to make the SEAKNOT resulting research roadmap a reality through their upcoming projects portfolio.

3. MAJOR PROGRESS

Since its inception in October 2022, SEAKNOT has made a substantial progress in all the areas addressed. Here below an update of the most meaningful ones is synthesized.

3.1. PIRTSA: Phenomena Identification and Ranking Table on Severe Accidents

As stated above, the SA PIRT is the core of SEAKNOT. The main purpose is to identify those SA areas/phenomena which should be given most attention when launching new R&D activities, either because they dominate the remaining uncertainties or because they have got a substantial potential to mitigate SA consequences. The PIRT scope is extended to the SA entire domain, including in-vessel, ex-vessel, containment, and source term areas. Likewise, WC-SMRs and near-term ATFs are being also considered.

Nearly 20 years ago, the EURSAFE project [2] set a historic milestone by building a soundly grounded PIRT on SA by reducing more than one thousand identified phenomena to about one hundred of them deserving further investigation, as they were both important for safety and still lacking sufficient knowledge. About ten years later, driven by the Fukushima-Daiichi accident in Japan in 2011, two independent studies were conducted by Japanese organizations and USA ones. The former addressed specifically source term issues resulting from the accident aftermath [10], whereas the latter was closer to a technology gap analysis [11]. In the European land, SNETP/NUGENIA-TA2 periodically published SA research priorities, mostly of a qualitative nature though [12]. This short list of works provide orientation in PIRTSA, which will be fed additionally by technical and State-Of-the-Art (SOAR) reports as well as by major outcomes from research projects conducted under different frames. References [13-19] are just some examples of them.

The first step when facing a PIRT on SA is to adapt the work initially proposed in the field of thermal-hydraulics and Design Basis Accidents (DBA) [6] to the SA specific domain. In addition to [10], a few applications in the SA domain have been reported [17, 20] recently, but they were restricted to specific systems and scenarios, i.e., in-vessel melt retention and spent fuel pools (SFPs), respectively.

The specific problem the PIRT addresses is the identification of the SA issues which research would lead to better characterize and, if possible, reduce uncertainties, as well as to efficiently enhance mitigation of SA consequences. The focus is on the potential issues effect on source term, i.e., radiological releases from the Nuclear Power Plant (NPP), specifically on onset time, rates and composition of the releases to the environment of a selection of radionuclides: I131; I132; Cs137; Ru106; Te132; Kr88; Xe133; Xe135. The drastic difference expected in source term between the in-vessel and the ex-vessel phases recommends to split accident sequences accordingly.

Ranking consists in assessing the relative importance of processes and phenomena with respect to the evaluation criteria selected as parameters of interest. The research priority is being assessed based on existing knowledge and safety significance of each phenomenon; each of these concepts split in three levels (i.e., low, L; medium, M; high, H). Knowledge is weighed on data availability and representativeness, and modeling maturity; as in the case of priority, three levels are given to both data and models. Figure 4 shows how knowledge and safety significance combine to define priority. It is high priority (H) whenever knowledge is poor (L) and safety significance is high. Low priority is attributed whenever safety

significance is low and/or existing knowledge is high. The rest of cases (3), is given a medium ranking level but ordered by priority: the maximum (M1) given to high safety significance and the minimum (M3) to mid-impacting phenomena on which there is some knowledge.

		Safety Significance		
		Low	Medium	High
Knowledge	Low	L (Poor understanding; irrelevant)	M2 (Poor understanding; mild effect)	H (Poor understanding; impacting)
	Medium	L (Some understanding; irrelevant)	M3 (Some understanding; mild effect)	M1 (Some understanding; impacting)
	High	L (Sound understanding; irrelevant)	L (Sound understanding; mild effect)	L (Sound understanding; impacting)

Figure 4. PIRT ranking

In Figure 5 the structure of the table used to list and rank phenomena is displayed.

Ref. Number	Phenomenon	Short Description	Comp/ Sub-system	Accident Phase	Knowledge		Safety Significance	Priority	Refs.	
					Data	Model			D	M
C-1	Homogeneous steam condensation	Phase change of steam in a gas atmosphere driven by a local oversaturation	N.A.	In-v	H	M	L	L	D	[1], [2]
									M	[3]
ST-1									D	
									M	

C-Containment; ST- Source Term; In-v – In-vessel; Ex-v – Ex-vessel; N.A. – Not Applicable

Figure 5. Basic PIRT template

At present phenomena has been listed in the in-vessel, ex-vessel, containment and source term domains and have been orchestrated in the two accident phases mentioned above. The criteria set to bring a phenomenon in the list have been: 1) playing a role in an accident scenario of interest and, 2) potential effect on the Figures Of Merit (FOMs) chosen. It is considered that evaluation of some phenomena might require conducting *ad-hoc* sensitivity studies.

3.2. VADD: Validation Database Directory

The use of validation databases plays a pivotal role in enhancing the accuracy and reliability of the computer codes employed for nuclear safety analysis by validating the underlying physics and mathematical models incorporated into these codes. Verification and validation efforts are extensively taken over by the code developers and code users for specific modeling implemented in their codes [21;22]. Moreover, joint activities with a focus on a specific subject have been organized by international agencies, such as OECD/NEA containment code validation matrix [23] or SNETP/NUGENIA CoreSOAR [18], to provide a “common” validation database.

However, as SA involve various sub-domains, including in-vessel, ex-vessel, containment, and source term, the available validation database matrices do not comprehensively cover all these sub-domains with the same level of detail, leaving gaps in the understanding and validation of codes across the entire spectrum of SA phenomena. Another challenge with the current validation database is the lack of a standard methodology for evaluating the quality and applicability of experimental data for code validation. Standardized criteria are essential for ensuring a systematic and consistent approach towards assessing the

suitability of data for different SA phenomena [24; 25]. Inconsistent data quality may pose challenges in accurately assessing the performance of SA analysis codes, leading to uncertainties in their predictions.

Addressing the above-mentioned shortcomings requires concerted efforts from the nuclear community, including researchers, regulatory bodies, and industry stakeholders, to enhance the quality, diversity, and relevance of the validation database for SA analysis codes. The SEAKNOT work package WP2 which follows a similar structure as WP1 has been tailored to answer the aforesaid needs of the validation database. For this purpose, the sub-work packages within WP2 focus on different SA sub-domains, namely in-vessel, ex-vessel, containment, and source term. The main outcome will be an up-to-date Validation Database Directory (VADD) of “relational data” prepared by conducting critical analyses of the existing SA database, with a clear definition of data suitability for modeling assessment and SA mitigation. While keeping the main focus on existing LWRs, the overall work scope also includes collecting relevant databases on advanced technologies, e.g., LW-SMRs and near-term ATFs.

As an outcome of the work done during the first year, a comprehensive literature review was performed based on a Template to collect SA database information as per pre-defined SA research sub-domains. In parallel, database information has also been collected on verification & validation matrices implemented in a number of the existing safety analysis codes, such as MELCOR, ASTEC, AC², GASFLOW. Indeed, the information on new/complementary validation data providing additional insights on a specific phenomenon modelled in these codes will also be of added value providing a possibility to update current V&Vs implemented in the aforesaid SA analyses codes. As the work is still in progress, any supplementary work done as part of WP1 related to sensitivity and uncertainty analyses to understand the impact of input parameters on the code predictions will further help in identifying the most influential parameters and their uncertainties, contributing to a more realistic representation of the code's predictive capabilities – further providing insights to look for a specific database.

The following elements have been considered during the review phase of experimental data:

- Relevance of experimental data; experimental data used for validation closely represents the physical phenomena occurring during severe accidents in light water reactors. The data should cover a wide range of accident conditions and scenarios.
- Applicability to various reactor designs; the validation database includes a diverse set of experimental data applicable to different light water reactor designs, such as pressurized water reactors (PWRs), boiling water reactors (BWRs) designs covering both large LWRs and WC-SMRs. This broadens the applicability of the severe accident analysis codes across various reactor types.
- Validation at different scales; validation at different spatial and temporal scales, from the molecular scale to the plant scale, ensures the accuracy of the code predictions in capturing the progression of complex events throughout the reactor system.
- Data used in code benchmarks; experiments that simulate severe accident scenarios and provide data for benchmarks. This encompasses datasets ranging from SET (Separate Effect Test) data for validation of a specific model, to IT (Integral Test) data for validation of an integral code. CET (Combined Effect Test) data have also been included for strongly linked phenomena for code module validation.
- Documentation; technical reports and any kind of scientific publications supports the credibility of the validation efforts and facilitates readily available information for use in the validation process by potential users of the proposed validation database.

The type and amount of experimental data collected so far are highlighted below in Fig. 6 by using an example of a database collected as part of the source term sub-WP. The collected database belongs to a broad spectrum of experimental facilities in Europe involved in source-term experimental research. A wide range of test characteristics, e.g. chemistry, fission product distribution, and material have been covered in

the experimental investigations conducted in these test facilities. To support in extrapolation of experimental results to the reactor scale, different facility scales and boundary conditions without any doubt are beneficial. Moreover, the application of instrumentation to provide measured data at different tempo-spatial resolutions is suitable for codes based on different modeling approaches, from empirical to mechanistic.

Fig.6. Test facilities contributing to the database on source term research

In parallel to the ongoing literature review activity to collect the experimental database information, the development of a methodology to assess and consolidate SA database to finally select data as part of VADD is also ongoing. Leveraging the consolidated SA expertise within SEAKNOT, the methodology aims to establish guidelines for assessing the quality and applicability of these databases, a crucial step in validating SA codes for specific phenomena. Lessons learned from the related database collection and evaluation activities, such as SAPIUM [24] and SNETP-NUGENIA IPRESKA [25] are being considered as a good basis to develop a larger scope methodology suitable for the assessment of the entire SA domain. The guidelines evolved as part of the methodology will not only identify missing information regarding a specific phenomenon of high interest as per current state-of-the-art but also facilitate the identification of complementary databases. Continuous updates will be informed by close interaction with WP1, ensuring responsiveness to knowledge gaps or newly recognized phenomena of safety significance. The main elements of the database assessment methodology are shown in Fig. 7. This check involves assessing the quality, representativity, and applicability of data, covering factors, such as spatial and temporal scales, boundary conditions, and relevant phenomena. The finalized database methodology is aimed to provide two main outcomes. First, an index for assessing the adequacy of experimental data based on available information on measured data and available documentation providing information on test protocol and other details as necessary for employing the data for validation purposes. Secondly, the establishment of criteria for classifying experimental databases as per their suitability for code validation. For this purpose, a mathematical expression relying on a point-based system for assessing the experimental data adequacy for code validation purposes is being evaluated. The mathematical expression will involve selected parameters of high importance as depicted in Figure 7, such as data accuracy, relevance to the modeled phenomena, coverage of representative boundary conditions, documentation, etc. The experimental data will be assessed for their suitability to each parameter and given a score based on a pre-defined scale. Finally, each evaluated dataset will be allocated a total score involving all parameters of interest to indicate their adequacy or not for code validation purposes. This work is currently in progress.

Figure 7. Elements of the database assessment methodology

Finally, to facilitate broader outreach of “database” findings beyond SEAKNOT, the development of an analytical tool “website” is foreseen to be launched at a later time within WP2. This relational database, inspired by existing thermal-hydraulic tools, e.g. OECD/NEA THIESYS, will not store experimental data online but will serve as a valuable resource for code validation and mitigation strategy assessments.

3.3. SAINET: SA infrastructure NETWORK

The SA roadmap coming out from SEAKNOT intends not just to highlight what the purpose of upcoming research should be, but also what conditions still need to be addressed and provide recommendations on how to do it. This holistic approach requires settling a broad view of infrastructures that would be necessary to do it. Some of which might already exist such as they are or need some adaptation, but some specific issues might need facilities and infrastructures currently not available. This is the main purpose of SAINET (SA Infrastructure NETWORK).

SAINET will cover all SA sub-domains: in-vessel, ex-vessel, containment response including hydrogen combustion risk, and source term. A special focus will be devoted on existing experimental facilities to evaluate the behavior of instrumentation under SA conditions, the performance of mitigation devices and their qualification, and new technologies upcoming in the near future, like WC-SMRs and ATFs.

To start with, a mapping of the current European experimental facilities investigating SA has been built. By surveying the entire European SA community, information has been collected on facilities (characteristics and materials), running teams (expertise and professional situation), data provided for SA codes validation, current and planned activities in the coming years, and open references including their contribution in recent years. As an illustration of the outcome from this activity, Figure 8 gives an overview of the phenomena that have been experimentally investigated in the recent past: source term & fission products, ex-vessel, in-vessel, pool scrubbing, and containment and H₂-risk.

Figure 8. Number of facilities involved in a severe accident topic

Beyond the statistical map of facilities and issues, there are a number of insights from this study that are worth highlighting: more than 20 European facilities do not have any planned activity ahead in the coming years; “critical competences” are threatened to get lost with no chance to transfer them in about 10 of them; and, currently few facilities are being used for WC-SMRs and ATFs research under SA conditions.

3.4. KNOS: KNOWledge Spreading

At present time, when some of the knowledge acquired in the SA field is at risk of being lost (as many specialists are retiring) and new approaches for the SA assessment (as UaSA) are being explored, it is an appropriate timing to articulate the most efficient ways possible to bring young generation on board to face the new research challenges in this field and, at the same time, preserving the high level of European expertise. Therefore, it is of utmost relevance to pass the current State-of-the-Art on SA - deriving from the technical WP1-WP3 - onto the generations who are inheriting such legacy. Consequently, the main expected outcomes from this WP4 KNOS are:

- A strengthening of background and skills of young generations in the SA field, by a range of dissemination and communication activities in which an internal mobility programme is the backbone of an efficient K2T from expert senior scientists and engineers together with the Severe Accident Phenomenology (SAP) Course and the new Severe Accident Summer Camp (SASCAMP).
- A vast and diverse Communication & Dissemination (C&D) plan, with particular emphasis on the transfer of the SEAKNOT technical outcomes beyond the partnership boundaries to broadly reach the international SA community through the ERMSAR (European Review Meeting on Severe Accident Research) Conferences but also through AB and EUG organizations, which might significantly increase the range of stakeholders reached out.

Activities in WP4 are carried out in 4 sub-WPs and will be performed for the whole duration of the project.

Under the general NUGENIA TA2 framework, two editions of the SAP short course (one week) have been planned in SEAKNOT (WP4.1). This SAP course, from its first edition in 2006, represents the only international course offered to train or to complete the training of persons recently involved in the SA field, focusing on the dissemination of the knowledge gained on SA in the last two decades with a program covering the SA phenomenology, progression and mitigation in current water-cooled reactors of Gen. II and III, but also the different design solutions in Gen. III NPPs and recently in SMRs. Lectures for these Courses are given by international experts from major nuclear institutes, industries and universities, with a strong

involvement of the SEAKNOT partners. A special focus is always on the Fukushima-Daiichi Severe Accident, but the course also includes background lectures on NPP safety and SA codes and their uncertainties. The main objective of these SAP short courses is the preservation of severe accident knowledge, the transmission to scientists and engineers dealing with reactor safety in either universities, R&D organizations, safety institutes, utilities or nuclear industry and the further development of expertise in the severe accident field.

The first SEAKNOT SAP course was held in Madrid on June 19-23, 2023, jointly co-organized by UPM Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, CEA - IRESNE, CIEMAT, University of Pisa and Jožef Stefan Institute. The technical programme, displayed in Figure 9, was defined by the *Steering Educational Committee*, together with the actions related to the choice of lecturers, among the best European experts in the field of Severe Accident phenomenology R&D, TSO and nuclear industry. and the assessment of the level of excellence of the Course itself This program covers a large initial part, introductory to the complex severe accident phenomenologies, including Source Term aspects, followed by more applicative specific lectures on the safety aspects, as SA codes and uncertainties or new design features in Gen III NPPs, decommissioning or SMRs.

Monday, June 19	Tuesday, June 20	Wednesday, June 21	Thursday, June 22	Friday, June 23
8:00-8:30 Registration				
8:30-9:00 Introd. Welcome (X.Y,UPM Director)				
9:00-10:00 1. Severe Accidents in NPP Safety	9:00-10:00 6. Late In-Vessel Phase	9:00-10:00 10. Ex-Vessel Phase - Part 2	9:00-10:00 14. SAMG	9:00-10:00 17. Decommissioning
10:00-11:00 2. TMI-2 Accident	10:00-11:00 7. Early Containment Failure	10:00-11:00 11 Source Term - Part 1	10:00-11:00 15. Nuclear Energy in Spain	10:00-11:00 18. New design Feature-Gen 3
11:00-11:30 Coffee Break	11:00-11:30 Coffee Break	11:00-11:30 Coffee Break	11:00-11:30 Coffee Break	11:00-11:30 Coffee Break
11:30-12:30 3. Chernobyl accident	11:30-12:30 8. Hydrogen Risk-Part 1	11:30-12:30 11 Source Term - Part 2	11:30-12:30 16. Radiological impact	11:30-12:30 19. SMRs
12:30-13h30 Lunch	12:30-13h30 Lunch	12:30-13h30 Lunch	12:30-13h30 Lunch	12:30-13h30 Lunch
13:30-14:30 4. Fukushima Accident-Part 1	13:30-14:30 8. Hydrogen Risk-Part 2	13:30-14:30 12. SA code & uncertainties-Part 1	Visit of SA facilities	13:30-14:30 Feedback and Conclusions
14:30-15:30 4. Fukushima Accident-Part 2	14:30-15:30 9. Steam Explosions -Part 1	14:30-15:30 12. SA code & uncertainties-Part 2		
15:30-16:00 Coffee Break	15:30-16:00 Coffee Break	15:30-16:00 Coffee Break		
16:00-17:00 5. Early In-Vessel Phase-Part 1	16:00-17:00 9. Steam Explosions -Part 2	16:00-17:30 13. Safety Assessment (PSA)		
17:00-18:00 5. Early In-Vessel Phase -Part 2	17:00-18:00 10. Ex-Vessel Phase - Part 1			

Figure 9. SAP 2023 technical programme

The attendance to this Course (Figure 10), the first in presence after the 2021 virtual edition forced by COVID-19 emergency, were the following: 27 professional and 33 students participants (13 were lecturers and 2 were UPM staff). In big numbers, organizations from 14 countries and people with about 20 nationalities attended.

Figure 10. SAP 2023 participants.

Next SAP 2025 edition will be organized from 23 to 27 June 2025 at Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ) and will be followed by the first edition of the SASCAMP initiative, also at FZJ. The SAP 2025 organization and the technical contents will be similar to the SAP 2023 ones, with further new/updated lectures (ATFs, SMRs and new methodology on UASA, etc.) for the second applicative part of the Course, while the following SASCAMP (30 June – 4 July 2025) will be intended to be a new format residential experience, not another SAP Course or a Sa code training. During this SASCAMP qualified “instructors”, different from the SAP instructors but with a planned strong collaboration, will pose a SA-related assignment (one single topic per day, i.e., in-vessel; ex-vessel; containment/hydrogen risk; source term; uncertainties) to participants and will support small groups of participants while “solving” the assignment by any means they might come up with (i.e., codes, models, data, “expert judgement”, ...), shearing their knowledge and knowhow in this area through practical applications of the theoretical knowledge.

Other traditional flagship of SNETP/NUGENIA TA2 that the SEAKNOT project has taken over is the organization of ERMSAR 2024 and 2026 conferences (WP4.2). ERMSAR generic objective is to provide an open forum to foster deep and practical exchanges in the SA area across the entire community. This conference, traditionally open to both NUGENIA and non-NUGENIA members, has become the only international event fully focused on SA, with room to discuss recent research results, new and innovative methodologies, and needs to better manage these potential events in case they happen again. From the last 10th ERMSAR edition in May 2022 organized by KIT in SNETP/NUGENIA/TA2 framework and gathering 118 participants from nearly 50 organizations settled in 21 countries worldwide, the scope of the conference also includes innovative nuclear technologies, such as ATFs, SMRs, fusion, etc. The first ERMSAR Conference in the SEAKNOT framework is the current 11th edition, hosted by KTH Stockholm, while the next one will be organized by CIEMAT Madrid in 2026.

The textbook “Nuclear Safety in Light Water Reactors - Severe Accident Phenomenology”, edited in 2011 by Bal Raj Sehgal [9], under the frame of the SARNET FP6 project, is foreseen to be extended (WP4.3). At the moment, this book is the only one-stop resource on how to assess, prevent, and manage SAs in LWRs. Nonetheless, the progress made by all the investigations conducted after the Fukushima-Daiichi accident and some innovative aspects brought in by nuclear technology (i.e., installation of new engineering safety systems, new insights into accident management, ATFs, and WC-SMRs, among others) recommend updating and extending it. The textbook nature as a walk-through knowledge and understanding SA complexity will be preserved, though, and by no means it is intended to end up in a

SEAKNOT C&D activities are giving emphasis on the transfer of the SEAKNOT technical outcomes beyond the project’s partners (WP4.4). Three major axis for these activities have been set: public

communication; external dissemination; and mobility of young researchers. A short description of each is given next:

- **Public communication:** A detailed C&D strategy plan has been developed with specific communication actions, key messages to get across and target audiences. To assess the impact of the plan, key performance indicators have been set. Additionally, a series of communication tools and actions have been already implemented, as the project logo (Figure 9) and the visual identity, including presentation and document templates, a roll-up and a flyer. Among them, a public project website (www.seaknot.com), yearly newsletters and a LinkedIn account to promote and advertise SEAKNOT outcomes and activities.

Fig. 9: SEAKNOT logo.

The main C&D activity in the first part of the project has been the participation to relevant public events, presenting and promoting SEAKNOT at international conferences and meetings (as ERMSAR 2022 at KIT Karlsruhe, SNETP Coordinators' Hub Day in Brussels, MUSA Final Open Workshop in Madrid and ICONE 30 Conference in Kyoto) as well as in fora (FISA 2022, NUGENIA TA2 General Meeting and SNETP 2023 Forum) and this activity will continue for the entire project duration.

- **External Dissemination.** The dissemination of SEAKNOT results should use any means available, particularly scientific joint and individual publications in peer-reviewed journals, and presentations in international conferences, workshops, seminars, working groups, etc. The first edition of an electronic newsletter has been released in October 2023 and will be issued at the end of each year of the project to inform stakeholders of the project's progress by using the foreseen SEAKNOT dissemination channels (public website, mailing list, LinkedIn account), and those of SNETP and ENEN too.
- **Mobility of young researchers.** A mobility program aims at training young researchers and PhD/Master students from consortium organizations through delegations in partners' laboratories to enhance the exchanges and the dissemination of knowledge. Additionally, the presence of these young students or researchers in international conferences, workshops, and seminars to present some SEAKNOT results, is also supported. During this initial period 7 actions have been just supported, including one long mobility, and 4 further actions are under approval of the ExB.

4. FINAL REMARKS

The SEAKNOT project was born to respond to the current circumstances and the forthcoming needs in the domain of SA. Awarded by the Euratom Research and Training Programme 2021-2023 (GA#101060327), SEAKNOT is aimed at and orchestrated to outline a SA research roadmap based on technical grounds and oriented to efficiently address issues that might significantly contribute to enhancing the safety of actual and next generation NPPs. This encompasses consideration of multiple aspects, among which special attention is being given to identifying the critical experimental infrastructure as part of the SEAKNOT roadmap together with knowledge transfer efforts for the strengthening of the workforce who will run SA in

vestigation in decades to come. It is foreseen that a suitable implementation of the roadmap will allow Europe to keep leading the area of SA research in Gen. II and III in the world in the coming decades, extending the scope to innovative technologies, like WC-SMRs and ATFs.

Since its inception in October 2022, SEAKNOT has achieved major progress. Having been described in the preceding sections, they are here summarized:

- A PIRT methodology has been proposed to address the challenge of a holistic approximation to the SA domain, which has required a proper adaptation of the original formulation. Oriented towards source term, both in-depth knowledge of significant phenomena and mitigation, the issue ranking process is to be conducted according to the SA phases (in-vessel and ex-vessel).
- An evaluation of the SA database for validation purposes has been drafted. The collected data are to be assessed in terms of representativeness and completeness based on a specifically developed methodology.
- A mapping of current European experimental facilities devoted to severe accident studies has been gathered. It is still too early to know if the existing infrastructure will be adequate for the forthcoming R&D demand, as this will depend on the PIRT outcome and the data base validation. Nonetheless, concerns about continuation of some facilities and preservation of skills in some running teams have been identified.
- An ambitious K2T plan has been articulated, with a well-supported mobility programme and a range of communication activities ongoing. The first SAP edition within SEAKNOT (SAP 2023) was held in Marid and met the expectations in terms of the technical programme, quality of lectures (material and delivery), attendance, venue and organization. The next edition of SAP course in SEAKNOT framework is scheduled in 2025 at FZJ (D), together with the first edition of SASCAMP initiative. As for ERMSAR 2024, the number of submissions has doubled the previous edition.

No matter how much has been already accomplished, SEAKNOT does have a path to go and it is foreseen a major direct impact in the domain of SA research in the coming decade.

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